

SHUKUR XOLMIRZAYEV'S ARTISTIC ANALYSIS OF VILLAGE CHARACTERS IN HIS STORIES

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Annotation: Shukur Xolmirzayev is a phenomenon in Uzbek literature. He has created a new school of storytelling with his unique style, spirituality, and works. In his short yet profound stories, the author skillfully depicts the human psyche and character in a remarkable manner. This article explores several of the author's stories, discussing the characters of village people, their way of life, and their societal significance. Overall, the protagonists in Xolmirzayev's stories are analyzed from an artistic perspective.

Keywords: Uzbek literature, Uzbek prose, author, stories, works, village people, character, style, societal life, spirituality, artistic analysis, truthfulness, image, event.

Shukur Xolmirzayev, a prominent figure in our literature, has dedicated his life to literature and is inherently gifted as a contributor. His works, which have emerged to date, are reaching our nation as "spiritual fruits". Colleagues naturally describe Shukur Xolmirzayev as straightforward, brave, and truthful. Indeed, readers who have read his works can attest to this. In particular, the writer himself expresses the following thoughts on truthfulness: "I've seen it myself: as time goes on, the opportunity to tell the truth or to avoid it arises. This is fortune for a writer! After all, what does a writer need? It's this freedom! What is the writer's duty? To tell the truth! Therefore, among the ancient tales told between world writers, there is one: the writer's essence is truth itself. Now, in such an environment, it is a great sin to stay unemployed, let alone interfere."The writer encapsulates these sentiments uniquely, leaving behind works of distinctive value. Despite being familiar with the creations and knowledge of world writers, he has not assimilated their values. On the contrary, he has inscribed the realities of life specific to the Uzbek nation's traditions and cultural truths.

While Shukur Xolmirzayev has also succeeded in other genres, it is primarily his addition to the genre of storytelling that distinguishes him. The reason lies in the fact that his stories are equivalent to a single tale or novel in terms of brevity and significance. From the faithful individuals who have entrusted their lives' most valuable details to the realm of artistic creation, Shukur Xolmirzayev appears as the writer's voice, and in his conversation with Safar Olloyor, a valuable explanation regarding storytelling is described, suggesting that "the subsequent generations may take an interest in storytelling to a noticeable degree. For example, there are so few stories in our newspaper's prose section. To ask authors, I will not write more - it is still possible."

In the context of that same character. For example, a woman who went out yesterday, dressed beautifully, happy, went for a walk with her children, but on her way back, she didn't have money for the bus... Here, the character's essence is revealed! Our president says: tell the truth, write the truth. No one can write the truth. Previously, there were few storytellers themselves, at least in a modest sense. "Stop the story in such a place that the hero's death or survival is determined," said Jack London. We need to find that point."

The author, in these words, is concerned about the integrity of the genre of storytelling. He urges his colleagues to write reality in their work, avoid falsehoods and fictions. During the Soviet era, our writers and poets were stifled, hiding reality and forced to write various fallacies. After gaining independence, there have been significant changes in literature as well. A new environment, new processes have emerged for creators. The author, in the same vein, says, "Let's get rid of the old clichés now," perhaps.

Shukur Xolmirzayev has beautifully illustrated the characters, psyche, and social lives of rural people in stories such as "The Death of the Shepherd," "Once Upon a Time," "One Friend, Two Friends," "Pigeons," and others. For example, in the story "Once Upon a Time," through the characters O'sar, Maqsad Momo, and Hojar, the author vividly portrays the rural environment and the characters' peculiarities. After Maqsad Momo's son dies in battle, his wife takes her two sons and leaves. Momo, on the other hand, sends them to a matchmaker. In the story, a fellow bride decides not to give him any torment, even though she wanted to tear him apart with his stripes, and Momo, who had been dragged away and left to handle the difficulties and troubles of life, is depicted in a mythological style. O'sar takes Momo's corpse and takes it to the tree, as well as an example of the mythological myth from the past in the story.

In summary, the author's work is characterized by accurate language. The inner sentiments, physical condition, and essence of the characters are all transparent. At one point, good, while in the other, negative qualities are depicted in the internal struggles of characters with deeper thoughts, and thoughtful, and spiritually deep thoughts. With a style that emphasizes the use of individualized speech.

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